

Psychosocial and Social Effects of Social Media

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Abstract:

The objective of this study is to bring the negative psychological and social effects of using social sharing nets. Problems on a social scale in today's world show that how functional and effective social networks are. On an individual scale, psychological traumas that derived from using social sharing nets can well be observed in visual and printed media. People find it hard to put a limit to their use of social sharing nets but keeps pushing their limits forward. The areas of social and individual approval and denial are completely problem. Social networks encourage the limitlessness in the degeneration of the social structure. However Facebook should not be considered only from the point of negativity.

Social sharing networks encourage individuals to become more free psychologically so that the understanding based upon democracy and human rights would be improved. The main issue here to consider is to have enough information. So it must be more important to know how to do it. One of the significant activity areas of social Networks is perhaps to serve people not only their expectations but also what they would not expect. The real effective aspect is not the expectations which have become real but the realization of what has not been expected.

The data of the study gained by surveys – descriptive- were processed according to the identified variables with statistical methods. In the first section of the study, a field mission was held and a literature scan was performed. By referring back to the previously conducted studies, the methods and techniques were assigned. The objective of the study, problem status, hypothesis and finiteness, problem Question, population and sample, and methods were transferred into a table and thus information is provided in the second section. In the third section, the analyses of the data were performed with the relevant methods. In the fourth section, comments and suggestions were made in concordance with the processed data.

Key Words: *The Psycho-Social Effects of Facebook, Facebook and Its Personal Harm, Facebook and Individual Use of It.*

Introduction

Informatics Technologies have started covering up more space in our daily lives make it inevitable for all people to have new habits of life and construct new communication ways, which lead to learning and gaining new behaviour patterns that were not existent earlier and thus all these changes and differences result in positive or negative alterations in the lives of people (Dağ 2001: 24; Doğan 2006). According to Doğan (2006) technological changes in this sense both change human relations and give way to the employment of new channels of relation patterns.

“According to the survey that Psychology Department in Goteborg University conducted on a thousand people, internet users who follow others’ lives via facebook succumb to depression when they compare their own lives with others’. Leif Dent, a researcher in the group that conducted the survey, resembles this to a fake life and point out that “ It is the most enjoyable moments and pictures that people share on Facebook. This leads to an illusion in other people as one cannot possibly see the real life or really sad moments of the others on Facebook. Being jealous of others’ virtual lives due to the social Networks has become a recent problem that affects people” (Sabah, 06 March 2012)

Prior to the puberty phase and during puberty, overuse of social Networks and technology is believed to cause anxiety, depression and other psychopathologic issues (Doğan, A., 2006).”

“According to another research conducted by Oxford University, social Network websites such as Facebook or Twitter cause teenagers go into an “identity crisis”. Users, who share their pictures or opinions constantly on these websites are thought to be trying to attract others by giving the message “Look, here I am”. Professor Baroness Greenfield, head of the research, states that while friendships become bigger on the internet, our brains are somehow installed by electricity wires. Greenfield also adds that “banality has become a trend especially on Twitter. Why should anyone be interested in what the person s/he is following has eaten at breakfast or where s/he has gone to? This looks very much like what little children say to their parents continuously as in “Mum, look what have I done? / Mum, look, I can do this too.” Experts point out that spending most of your time on such websites causes attention deficit, the need for an instant happiness and a nonverbal communication.” (www.nnet.gen.tr)

Today, facebook is a social mass media instrument, on which many scientists perform researches and arrive at new findings and produce new data. In other words social sharing nets are very important data sources. Facebook users come together via various social sharing groups and pages and they form huge masses, moreover they also come together in real life and initiate many activities or protests. (Lead Actor of Revolutions; Internet . Habertürk , 22 February 2011 Tuesday)

Objective of the Study (Problem Status)

The objective of this study is to be informed about the negative or positive psychosocial and social effects of facebook, an important social network in our lives and its influences upon social relations and attitude and behaviours of people and its place in the lives of individuals and the duration that people spend their time in facebook and share the information with parents, and educators. Seeing the issue from this point of view, this study is of great significance and on the level of contributing to the solving of the internet sourced problems.

Facebook

Facebook got its name from "Paper Facebook." It is a form that students, lecturers, and employees at universities in the United States fill out to introduce themselves. Facebook currently has more than 800 million users worldwide.

Facebook is a social network that allows people to communicate and exchange information with their friends. Founded on February 4, 2004, Facebook was primarily for students at Harvard University. It became accessible to all email addresses on September 11, 2006. Users can join the groups they want based on where they work, live or study (tr.wikipedia.org 2012).

According to (tr.wikipedia.org 2012) and Alexa statistics, Facebook is the second most visited website in the world as of October 31, 2010. It is also the most visited website in Canada, South Africa and South Africa. Facebook is the second most visited website in Norway, the UK and Sweden, the third most visited website in Egypt and Panama, and finally the fifth most visited website in the US,

Australia and Turkey. It clearly shows that it is a website that he has visited. they spend time on people and they are affected (Chou, C.J. & Nay & Ching, N, 1998).

Tech Crunch, 85% of students in the US have a Facebook account, and 60% of them go online every day. 85% go online every week and 93% every month. Facebook spokesperson Chris Hughes confirms that Facebook users spend an average of 19 minutes on websites each day (tr.wikipedia.org 2012). With the reference of (tr.wikipedia.org), the fact that there are 30.5 million Facebook users in Turkey as of September 2011 shows how effective and important it is on the lives of people living in Turkey. According to (www.socialbakers.com) data, the rate of male Facebook users is 63% and the rate of female users is 37% in Turkey. When we look at the problem especially as of 2023 and 2024 in Turkey, internet users have increased at a significant rate as in all the world and it has now become a chronic addiction that affects social life. In order to eliminate this addiction, "Solution-Focused Short-Term Psychological Counseling" practices will be needed, as in the treatment of other psychological disorders.

Social and Psychological Effects of Facebook

The impact of Facebook on society is undeniable. It has changed the way we interact with each other, and has even become a crucial tool for networking and job searching. However, Facebook has also been criticized for its privacy policies, and has been blamed for spreading fake news and spreading hate speech. Despite these criticisms, Facebook remains one of the most popular social media platforms in the world, and it continues to shape the way we interact with each other. In conclusion, Facebook has had a profound impact on society. It has changed the way we connect with each other and has become an important tool for businesses and individuals alike. Despite its controversies and criticisms, Facebook remains one of the most significant platforms in the world and will likely continue to shape our lives for years to come.

While social networks (social networks) that have become widespread in recent years obsess individuals, they also contribute to the birth of a purposeless and arrogant generation. Even when breaking up with their boyfriends or girlfriends, young people only use facebook by changing their relationship status (Cengizhan, C., 2003). According to the statement made by Facebook, 43,869,800 people changed their relationship status to "single" in 2010 and 3,025,791 people declared their relationship status as "complicated". (www.nnet.gen.tr)

Use of Facebook and Its Relation with Self-Confidence

Realizing that more than 560 million people around the world spend a significant part of their time on Facebook every day, sociologists and psychologists began to conduct serious research on this issue and reached interesting findings. It is claimed that the use of Facebook, which is the basis of many scientific claims, causes health problems and people miss potential job opportunities, at the same time, it deepens the feelings of jealousy of users, turning them into "monsters" and making them more. is a narcissist (Aksüt, M. & Ateş, S. & Çelikkanat, A., 2012).

According to research by experts at York University in Canada, people who frequently update their status are often narcissistic or have low self-esteem issues.

Research by psychologists at the University of Georgia in 2008 revealed that many updaters have narcissistic tendencies. Emphasizing that narcissism is not just trying to attract attention and needing to be loved, psychologists state that this situation also supports the inability to maintain long-term reliable relationships.

Research by the University of York highlights that while girls focus more on posting attractive pictures, boys focus on praising themselves in the "About" section of their Facebook page. Facebook users, in particular, who have a lot of friends update their status too often, causing either their popularity to increase or their updates to be lost among many other updates. Social research shows that people prefer to work, live or have fun with those like them (Ellison, N.B. & Stainfield, C. & Lampe, C., 2007).

Experts at Cornell University confirm that Facebook users tend to assume that their friends on their friend lists share the same opinions as them. In the study, Facebook users were asked to state their preferences on divisive political issues and then asked to make a guess as to what their friends

might think about the same topics, but their predictions were often wrong, so researchers are mistaken in believing that "people" often agree with their friends."

“Facebook Users Could Be Affected by Their Friends’ Happy Pictures”

Hui Tzu, Grace Chou and Nicholas Edge, faculty members of the Department of Sociology at Utah Valley University in the USA, approached the subject with a scientific approach and reached an impressive conclusion. According to research, Facebook can make us unhappy. The images or videos that users upload are usually taken when people are happy. Photos on Facebook are usually of people who were happy, smiling and enjoying their time when those photos were taken. Such pictures cause the viewers' perceptions to be shaped around happiness, joy and pleasure. But is that true? People always smile at the targets and want to take pictures of these pleasant moments that they want to last forever (Kim, O.S. & Hong, H.Y., 1998). You're less likely to come across photos of other users' unhappy times. This confirms the unhappiness of those who look at that painting. According to the unhappy person who looks at the happy pictures of others, he is happy but not himself, and that unhappy person will also fall into the illusion that other people are happier than he is (www.candanblog.com).

Another result reached in the survey of the research is that there is a direct correlation between the time spent on Facebook and the state of believing that one's friends are happier than they are. That is, a person who spends more time on Facebook believes more strongly that their friends are happier than they are and that the world is not a fair place (www.candanblog.com).

One of the most important results of the research is that people who prefer to socialize with their friends in real life feel happier than those who prefer to socialize in virtual life (www.candanblog.com).

Facebook Can Cause Psychological Disorders on Teenagers

While the influence of Facebook is increasing, especially young people are under its influence. Dr Larry Rosen and Professor of Psychology Dominguez Hills from California State University conducted a study on how technology affects young people (www.zdnet.com).

According to Rosen, three possible negative effects of Facebook are as follow:

- *Teens who are addicted to Facebook are more likely to be narcissistic and display more anti-social behavior, manic disorder, and aggressive attitudes..*
- *Media and technology make young people more vulnerable to anxiety, depression and other psychological disorders.*
- *Facebook can confuse you more and negative learning can affect you.*

According to Rosen, three possible possible effects of Facebook are as follow:

- *Teens who spend more time on Facebook show more virtual empathy towards their friends on their friend list.*
- *Social Networks can provide more interesting learning tools.*
- *Social Networks can help introverted young people socialize more.*

Students, who spend a lot of time on Facebook have lower grades in their lessons.

A psychologist from Holland, Paul Krischner found out that students, who check on Facebook from time to time while they are studying are unsuccessful in their lessons (Greenfield, D., 1999). Krischner conducted a research on 219 American students at university and confirmed that Facebook user students have a 3.06 average grade out of 5 while non-user students have an average of 3.82 out of 5. Psychological researches conducted in Ohio University in 2009 show that using Facebook seriously affects students' success in learning. According to this, "stalking your ex-girlfriend / ex-boyfriend on Facebook makes you fail your lessons" (Milliyet, 17 March 2011).

People Visit Their Facebook Accounts In The Morning Before They Visit The Bathroom

Oxygen Media and the Lightspeed Research Center reached impressive results in their research on Facebook users aged 18 to 34. mornings and 39% define themselves as Facebook addicts (Çelik, Ş., 2007). 49% consider hacking and controlling their boyfriends' Facebook accounts as a normal behavior (Milliyet, 17 March 2011).

As Regards To Facebook Making People Happy

The British Computer Society, BCS, defies the myth that spending too much time on social networks will isolate people and drive them away from real life. According to a study by BCS, using social networks such as Facebook has a statistically significant effect on people's satisfaction with their lives. This positive effect is higher in people with low income, low education level, and women (Milliyet, 17 March 2011).

According to (www.socialbakers.com), the distribution of users according to their ages in Turkey is as follow:

18 – 24 years old; 34% users, age 25-34 29%, age 35-44 13%, age 45-54 5%, age 55-64 1%, and age 65-0 1%.

Features of Facebook

According to (tr.wikipedia.org 2012)

“Photos: People can share their photos with friends on Facebook and tag themselves or their friends. Due to some privacy issues, Facebook has placed some limitations on the viewing of photos. As of August 2007, there are 31.31 billion photos on Facebook, which means 31 photos per person. Photos can be viewed by anyone, but cannot be seen by anyone if the settings are changed.

Nudge: Nudge is used to nudge a friend to start a dialogue.

Events: With the Events application, people can create and organize a meeting event, and other users can tell whether they will attend the event by RSVP*. (*"repondezs'ilvousplaît")

Videos: Facebook's video app allows users to post videos on video sharing sites like Youtube to each other, as well as post user-created videos in both statuses and private messages.

Language Options: The languages available in the translation app are: German, Czech, simplified Chinese, traditional Chinese, Hong Kong Chinese, Danish, Finnish, French, Welsh, Flamm, Spanish, Swedish, Italian, Japanese, Catalan, Korean, Polish, Bokmål Norwegian , Brazilian Portuguese, Turkish, Kurdish, Galician, Hungarian, Romanian, Slovenian, Thai, Albanian, Azerbaijani and Russian. Facebook's language support means that people of all nationalities can easily engage in interactive relationships with one another.

Facebook Status: Facebook's Status app allows users to let their friends or groups know about what they're doing or thinking. For example, the user might type “on vacation” in the status box. Status Updates are shown in the "last updated" tab in the friends list. Create and organizing events is an application that users use when they want to organize a meeting or give information about an event. Features of communication on facebook/social sharing nets.

Direct Communication: The type of communication in which the sender and receiver of the message are both online.

A. Synchronization: Considering the time direction, communication devices are classified as synchronous and asynchronous. If the communication between the sender of the message and the prescription is made synchronously, it is in the category of synchronous communication (Timisi 2003: 125; Doğan 2006). Users can have synchronous written and audio-visual communication with the camera function.

Instant Messaging: A type of instant textual communication between two or more people on Facebook.

Video Chat: *It is a type of online audio-visual communication between two or more people on Facebook.*

Being Asynchronous: *If the communication does not take place in the same time period or there is a time gap between sending and receiving the message, it is called asynchronous communication and are examples of books, newspapers, sound recordings, CDs and floppy disks. (Timisi: 2003: 125; Doğan 2006). One such feature of Facebook allows users to send and receive messages even when they are not online.*

Sharing on Another User's Wall: *A user can post text, photo, video, link, etc. on another user's wall. It is the type of communication that can be shared.*

Pokes: *The Poke app allows one user to poke another user to start a dialog(en.wikipedia.org 2012)*

Messages: *A textual communication feature between two or more users.*

Indirect Communication: *It is the type of communication where the description of the message is online but the sender is not online.*

1. Tagging: *The user can select a photo by tagging and add their friends' names on it, and the tagged users will receive notification after tagging and the tagged user can delete their name from the photo at any time.*

2. Like: *A Facebook user can like something posted by another user, which sometimes starts a conversation.*

3. Comments: *A Facebook user can write what he or she thinks about the post shared by another user. Comments where Facebook users who are members of the same group can start a conversation by liking or commenting. For example, a user can send a message or friend request to another user who likes or comments on a post in the group, whether he is a member of a group or not, and initiates communication."*

METHOD

This section contains information on the research population, research sample and data collecting tools, studies of validity and reliability of tools, collecting and analysis of data.

Model of the Research

In this study, descriptive methods were employed to find out the psychological and social effects of using social sharing nets/facebook on individuals. By using the screening method, conceptual and theoretical information were gathered and chosen to form the academical dimension of the study. Data collecting survey, which was prepared after some specific processes employed by the researcher, was used in the practice aspect. Questions in the survey were specifically selected according to their degrees of serving the purpose of the study and after opinions of the experts in the Faculty of Education were taken.

Data Collecting Tool

The survey consists of 8 questions on personal information and 5 questions on the way the individual uses Facebook, and a total of 39 questions were prepared and given to the sample group. As mentioned earlier, the data collecting tool was prepared in concordance with the survey preparation technique and processes. Opinion of the experts in the field were taken into consideration.

Sample

Facebook users, who are students at high school and university and live in Kars and whose ages are 16 and above were chosen at random and given the survey on the spot and one-to-one.

Population

The sample group represents the Facebook users whose ages are 16 and above. This means that the population of the study covers facebook users, ages of who are 16 and above.

Restrictions

The fact that even 5-year-old people use Facebook made it necessary to make a restriction and ignore that age group and limit the study to people 16 year old and above. The study is limited to the people given the survey and their answers.

APPLICATION

Evaluation of the Data

Relation Between the Facebook Use and Gender

Table-1: I use facebook to know new and different persons.

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Fbk1 Male	36	27,74	998,50	,003
Female	31	41,27	1279,50	
Total	67			

Table-2: I use facebook for intertainment and spare time activity

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Fbk2 Male	36	33,82	1217,50	,932
Female	31	34,21	1060,50	
Total	67			

Table-3: I use the Facebook to have more friends

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Fbk3 Male	36	28,64	1031,00	,00
female	31	40,23	1247,00	
Total	67			

Table-4: I use Facebook for the aim of playing games

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Fbk4 Male	36	28,64	1031,00	,009
Female	31	40,23	1247,00	
Total	67			

Table 5: I use Facebook for communication and chat

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Fbk5 Male	36	32,12	1156,50	,379
Female	31	36,18	1121,50	
Total	67			

The difference between male and female users about using Facebook to meet new and different people was found to be 0,05 ($P < 0,05$). This difference is in favor of female participants. Because they preferred negative choices and these alternatives' total scores are higher than positive ones. The order of the alternatives are from positives to negatives such as; 1-Everytime, 2- Often, 3-Sometimes, 4-Rarely, 5-Never. The difference that is in favour of the women can be attributed to the fact that they cannot express themselves freely.

There is no meaningful difference (on the level of 0,05) between men and women regarding the question above Table-2. ($P > 0,05$). No significant difference has been detected between men and women about why they use the internet.

It can be said that there is a meaningful difference (0,05) between men and women regarding the question above; "I use Facebook to make friends" in terms of gender. ($p < 0,05$). This difference is negative and in favour of the women and it confirms with the previous question depending on the negative alternatives such as 3-Sometimes, 4-Rarely, 5-Never. Because their score points are higher. It is understood that women cannot act freely in the society but they feel themselves safer and they can act as they wish on Facebook.

The answers to the question regarding playing games are shown above and there is a meaningful negative difference (0,05) in favour of the women ($0,05 > 0,009$), which can be related to the social and cultural environment of the women.

Regarding the answers given in Table 5, there is not a meaningful relation between men and women according to the level of $p = 0,05$ meaningfulness. ($,379 > ,05$). Subjects in both groups can be said to be using the internet- Facebook with the same motives.

Relation Between the Gender and Facebook Behaviour and Attitude.

Table -6: Is it necessary to be friends with unknown persons on Facebook?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG1 Male	36	28,32	1019,50	,003
Female	31	40,60	1258,50	
Total	67			

Table-7: Is it necessary to make friends with some known persons on Facebook?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG2 Male	36	31,42	1131,00	,018
Female	31	37,00	1147,00	
Total	67			

Table-8: Is it necessary to meet someone face to face you know on Facebook for the first time?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG3 Male	36	25,39	914,00	,00
Female	31	44,00	1364,00	
Total	67			

A meaningful difference at the level of $p : 0,05$ was found in terms of gender regarding the question at Table-6, ($P < 0,05$ ($,003 < 0,05$)). It is a negative difference. The difference that is in favour of the women confirms with the values in the previous table.

There is a meaningful difference at the level of $p : 0,05$ between men and women answering the question in Table-7. Because ($,05 > ,018$). This table such as previous tables show that the negative difference is in favour of women participants depending on their fears about making friends with

people whom s/he knows via Facebook.

The answers given to the question in Table-8 are as above and there is a meaningful negative difference between the preferences. 0,05 ($.00 < 0,05$) The difference is in favour of women and also it may be said that the women are very anxious about using Facebook.

Table-9: Should the making friend wish of someone that you don't know be considered by you on Facebook?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG4 Male	36	29,72	1070,00	,034
Female	31	38,97	1208,00	
Total	67			

Table-10: Must you have very friendly chats with someone you know on Facebook but you don't know in reality about yourself?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG5 Male	36	30,26	1089,50	,034
Female	31	38,34	1188,50	
Total	67			

Table-11: Must the relations on Facebook be accepted as important as the relations in real life?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG6 Male	36	35,28	1270,00	,522
Female	31	32,52	1008,00	
Total	67			

Table-12: Does the sharing of images such as special pictures or videos published on Facebook make you feel yourself well?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG7 Male	36	30,28	1090,00	,081
Female	31	38,32	1188,00	
Total	67			

Table-13: Do you feel about yourself bad when your updates (sharings) on Facebook are not seen/paid attention by your friends?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG8 Male	36	31,19	1123,0	,183
Female	31	37,26	1155,00	
Total	67			

There is an unignorable meaningful difference between men and women answering the question in terms of gender. At 0,05 $p=0,034 < 0,05$ ($.05 > ,034$). The difference is also negative and in favour of female ones. It can be said that women participants have negative answers for this

questionnaire question and they are not very eager to accept the friendship requested from someone whom s/he does not know (Table-9).

Analysing the answers, according to Table-10, a meaningful difference is apparent between the genders. As in the previous questions' answers, the difference is negative and in favour of the women and the reason for this is unclear but it can be attributed to the sociocultural influences. At 0,05 , $p=0,034 < 0,059$.

Analysing the answers to the question in Table-11, there is no meaningful difference between the genders. At P: 0,05 $0,05 < 0,522$.

Subjects answering the survey question in Table-12 put their approaches and it is found out that there is no meaningful difference between the genders in terms of their preferences and comments. It can be said that both men and women think similiarly about this question. At P:0,05 , $,081 > 0,05$.

The answers given to the question in Table-13 show that there is not a meaningful difference between men and women. At 0,05 , $,183 > 0,05$.

Table-14: Do you feel yourself happy when many of your friends are online on Facebook?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG9 Male	36	30,31	1091,00	,083
Female	31	38,29	1187,00	
Total	67			

Table-15: Does the highly appreciation of your sharings on Facebook make you feel respect?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG10 Male	36	33,31	1199,00	,746
Female	31	34,81	1079,00	
Total	67			

Table-16: Must a special time be allowed for Facebook using?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG11 Male	36	36,17	1302,00	,316
Female	31	31,48	976,00	
Total	67			

Table-17: Do you think that the Facebook steals the time you shared for the daily activities?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG12 Male	36	38,56	1388,00	,029
Female	31	28,71	890,00	
Total	67			

The answers given to the question in Table-14 show that there is not a meaningful difference between men and women. Both can be said to be sharing the similiar feelings. $0,05' te, 0,083 > 0,05$.

Analysing the answers given to the question in Table-15, it can be said that there is not a meaningful difference in terms of gender. At P:0,05 , $0,746 > 0,05$. It is understood that both genders have the same feelings.

Answers given to the question in Table-16 point out that there is no meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. At 0,05, 0,316>0,05. It can be said that either group thinks that a special amount of time should be spared for Facebook.

Answers given to the question in Table-17 suggest that there is a meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. The difference is in favour of men. The difference is negative. Because the male participants' preferences focused on the negative alternatives of the questionnaire. And also P:0,05, 0,029<0,05. It may be said that men doesn't aware of time and also they have enough time to be online on Facebook.

Table-18: Must the friends on Facebook be chosen according to their gender/sex?

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG13Male	36	35,81	1289,00	,394
Female	31	31,90	989,00	
Total	67			

Table-19: The friends on Facebook must be chosen according to the common interests

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG14 Male	36	33,28	1198,00	,735
Female	31	34,84	1080,00	
Total	67			

Table-20: I choose my friends on Facebook according to their jobs

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG15Male	36	32,56	1172,00	,479
Female	31	35,68	1106,00	
Total	67			

Table-21: I choose my friends on Facebook according to their favourite teams

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG16 Male	36	34,12	1228,50	,942
Female	31	33,85	1049,50	
Total	67			

Table-22: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the places they live in

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG17Male	36	34,01	1224,50	,994
Female	31	33,98	1053,50	
Total	67			

There is no meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender analysing the answers given to the question in Table-18. At 0,05 , 0,39>0,05.

There is no meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender analysing the answers given to the question in Table-19. Either group can said to be giving importance to the aspect of common interest. At $P:0,05$, $0,735 > 0,05$.

Analysis of the choices made and answers given to the question in Table-20 show that there is not a meaningful difference in terms of gender even if it is small. At $P:0,05$, $0,479 > 0,05$.

The analysis of the choices made in Table-21 show that there is no meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. Either group can be said to have based their choices on similiar reasons. At $0,05$, $,994 > 0,05$.

According to the comments made to the statement mentioned in Table-22, there is no meaningful difference in their choices between men and women. Because at $0,05$, $,994 > 0,05$.

Table-23: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the ethnicities of them

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG18Male	36	34,07	1226,50	,968
Female	31	33,92	1051,50	
Total	67			

Table-24: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the education levels of them

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG19Male	36	35,60	1281,00	,398
Female	31	32,15	996,50	
Total	67			

Table-25: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the sex they look for

Cinsiyt	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG20 Erkek	36	32,78	1180,00	,486
Bayan	31	35,42	1098,00	
Toplam	67			

Table-26: I choose my friends on Facebook by looking at their photographs

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG21 Male	36	33,81	1217,00	,920
Female	31	34,23	1061,00	
Total	67			

Table-27: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the music they listen to

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
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FbG22 Male	36	33,61	1210,00	,821
Female	31	34,45	1068,00	
Total	67			

Table-28: I choose my friends on Facebook according to their political thought

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG23 Male	36	36,81	1325,00	,142
Female	31	30,74	953,00	
Total	67			

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-23, it can be said that there is not a meaningful difference in their choices between men and women in terms of gender. Because at $0,05 > 0,968 > 0,05$.

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-24, it can be seen that there is not a meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. $0,398 > 0,05$.

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-25, it can be said that there is not a meaningful difference in their choices between men and women in terms of gender. $0,05 < 0,486$.

The data from the Table-26 show that there is no meaningful difference between male and female participants preferences about the poll question/sentence of “I choose my friends on Facebook by looking at their photographs”. Because; $,920 > 0,05$. It may be said that male and female participants have nearly the same or similar ideas to choose friends on Facebook by looking at their photographs or not.

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-27, it can be thought that there is not a meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. $0,05 < 0,821$.

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-28, it is seen that there is not a meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender. $0,05 < 0,142$.

Table-29: I choose my friends on Facebook according to the positions of their social relation

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
FbG24 Male	36	32,57	1172,50	,415
Female	31	35,66	1105,50	
Total	67			

According to the comments made to the statement in Table-29, it can be said that there is not a meaningful difference in their choices between men and women in terms of gender. $0,05 < 0,415$.

Table-30: Gender/sex and Facebook use with nickname

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Nickname Face Male	36	33,42	1203,00	,669
Female	31	34,68	1075,00	
Total	67			

Table-31: Gender/sex and how many Facebook accounts the participants had

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
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Nickname Face	Male	36	35,86	1291,00	,221
Accounts	Female	31	31,84	987,00	
	Total	67			

Table-32: Gender/sex and weekly average time/duration of Facebook use

Gender		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Gender and Weekly Average facebook Using Time	Male	36	34,44	1240,00	,777
	Female	31	31,84	1038,00	
	Total	67			

Table-33: Gender/sex and number of friends on Facebook

Gender		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Gender and Facebook Member of Friends	Male	36	36,64	1319,00	,218
	Female	31	30,94	959,00	
	Total	67			

Gender		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Sig.
Gender and The Form of Communication on Facebook	Male	36	32,03	1153,00	,349
	Female	31	36,29	1125,00	
	Total	67			

According to the tables; 30, 31, 32, 33, 34 (Gender/sex and Facebook use with nickname, Gender/sex and how many Facebook accounts the participants had, Gender/sex and weekly average time/duration of Facebook use, Gender/sex and number of friends on Facebook, Gender/sex and the form of communication on Facebook) it may be said that there is no meaningful differences between the preferences of men and women participants in return for “Gender/sex and Facebook use with nickname, Gender/sex and how many Facebook accounts the participants had, Gender/sex and weekly average time/duration of Facebook use, Gender/sex and number of friends on Facebook, Gender/sex and the form of communication on Facebook”. Because $0,05 < ,669 - ,221 - ,777 - 218 - ,349$.

Conclusion and Suggestions

The fact that information technologies have a prominent and rapidly increasing place in our lives obliges the individuals take up new habits and use new types of communication in life. Thus, learning new patterns of behaviour that were previously non-existent and adding them into their repertoire of attitude lead to positive or negative changes in the lives of individuals (Dağ 2001: 24 ; Doğan 2006). It is thought that overusing social networks and technology causes anxiety, depression and other psychopathological complaints in the pre-puberty and puberty phase of an individual. Facebook comes with various educational issues that cause inconvenience for the students who have difficulty using it during a reasonable amount of time. This, eventually leads to having a virtual perception of life in the young, who have the misconception that all individual relations are based upon this virtual arguments of the virtual world. The young lack the active and direct participation of real life, therefore they cannot internalise the cognitive, affective and motor skills and they are imprisoned in a virtual world in which there are inner windows that open to different interiors through a Facebook account by which they fictionalise a virtual world and establish a different type of

communication that conforms with neither the sameness nor oppositeness of real life. Because a good communication has its own set of rules, which confirm the fact that body language and the way of saying something are more important than the words written. As it is known, it is not what you say but it is how you say something, which underline the importance of the body language and the way you say something rather than the words. Words have a 10% influence in the process of communication and the language used on Facebook is apparently a nonstandart language that breaks the rules in general.

In the research conducted, it can be said that there are some significant differences about using Facebook between men and women in terms of personal behaviours and attitude. However there are no important differences between men and women in terms of most of the behaviours and attitude

Analysis of the answers to the survey question “Do you think Facebook steals from your time for your daily tasks?”, it can be said that there is a meaningful difference in terms of gender and the difference is in favour of the men at $p:0,05$, $0,029 < 0,05$. It can be concluded that men need more time for Facebook and they can be thought to be having more difficulties in fulfilling their daily tasks. Analysis of the answers to the survey question “Do you think one should be involved in sincere chats about him/herself with someone whom s/he has known only via Facebook?” shows that there is a meaningful difference in terms of gender. The difference, the reason of which is not understood but can be attributed to the sociocultural influences, is in favour of women and it is a negative difference. Because females answers focused on the negative alternatives such as; 4-Rarely and 5-Never at $0,05$, $p=0,034 < 0,05$.

Analysis of the answers to the survey question “Do you think one should accept a friendship request from someone whom s/he does not know?” confirms that there is an unignorable difference men and women in terms of gender at $0,05$, $p=0,034 < 0,05$ ($,05 > ,034$). The difference is in favour of women and it is negative. Because the alternatives of the questionnaire were ordered from positive to negative like; 1-Everytime, 2- Often, 3-Sometimes, 4-Rarely, 5-Never. Negative alternatives scores are higher. The reason for the difference can be attributed to the fact that women do not have enough opportunities to use facebook as much as men. On the other hand it may be thought that men don't have enough possibility to express themselves and also they need different means of communication techniques. However it is not right to meet the need by way of Facebook only and and it may even lead to more serious problems. In this case, integrating into the system like a virus to the cost of losing ties with the reality may have benefits in short term, however, on the other hand the social skills that are detached from the individual are far more important.

The analysis of the answers given to the question “Do you think one should accept a friendship request from someone whom s/he does not know?” shows that there is an unignorable meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender at $0,05$ ($p=0,034 < 0,05$ ($,05 > ,034$). The difference is also in favour of women and it is not positive it is negative. It means women don't agree with the question above. The reason for the difference that is in favour of women can be the same as the above mentioned reasons.

The analysis of the answers given to the survey question “Do you think one should meet someone, whom s/he has known on Facebook, face to face?” shows that there is a meaningful difference between men and women in terms of gender $0,05$ ($,00 < 0,05$). The reason for the difference can be the result of women's desire not to expand their social circle of connections as in the other questions, the answers of which show a meaningful difference. The difference is in favour of women and it is negative.

The analysis of the answers given to the survey question “Do you think one should make friends with people whom s/he knows via Facebook?” shows that there is a meaningful and negative difference at the level of $0,05$ in favour of women, and it can be said that that the possibilities in other options are confirmed.

The analysis of the answers given to the survey question “Do you think one should make friends on Facebook with people that s/he does not know?” shows that there is a meaningful negative difference at the level of $0,05$ between men and women in terms of gender. The negative difference is in favour of women $p < 0,05$ ($,003 < 0,05$). It can be concluded that women's attempts not to become more socialised stil continue. On the other hand men's attmpts become more socialised stil continue too.

The answers given and comments made to the statement “I use Facebook to play games” in the survey are shown in the related table, which shows that there is a meaningful difference in favour of women at the level of 0,05 ($0,05 > 0,009$). This difference is negative and most probably because of the women’s social and cultural environment.

The answers given and comments made to the statement “I use Facebook to make friends” confirm that there is meaningful difference in favour of women at the level of 0,05 between men and women in terms of gender ($p < 0,05$). It is understood that women, who cannot act as they wish in society, make use of Facebook, a more convenient and safer place according to their point of view but the cultural and social restrictions forces them not to use facebook as much as men.

The answers given and comments made to the statement “I use Facebook to meet new and different people.” show that there is a meaningful negative difference, between men and women at the level of 0,05 in favour of women and the reason for this can be the fact that women cannot express themselves in social life and this position very effective on Facebook using because they have social, cultural and economical difficulties on using Facebook as freely as they would like to.

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